

Community Participation In The Management And Utilization Of Forest Resources In The Traditional Forest Area In South Buton Regency, Southeast Sulawesi, Indonesia

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 24, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: September 30, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Community Participation, Forest Management, Forest Use, Customary Forest</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5542537</p>	<p><i>Community participation in the management and utilization of forest resources has a very strategic position in order to optimize the various existing potentials for improving community welfare so as to strengthen the capacity and role of the community in maintaining forest sustainability. This study specifically examines community participation in the management and utilization of forest resources in customary forest areas in South Buton district, Southeast Sulawesi, Indonesia. This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach. Data were collected from interviews, Focus Group Discussion (FGD) methods, and information from government policy documents. This study uses interactive data analysis techniques that include four components of the analysis process that takes place interactively, namely, data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. The conclusion of this study is that the management and utilization of forest resources in the customary forest area by the people of South Buton is carried out in a participatory collective manner in their daily lives. The activities of managing and utilizing forest resources are often associated with cultural views on the nature of the relationship between humans and nature. The people of South Buton still preserve the tradition of using forest resources based on cultural ideas that have been passed down and preserved from generation to generation. The people of South Buton use customary forests to obtain ecological benefits, social benefits, and economic benefits.</i></p>

Introduction

Community participation in forest management and utilization in Indonesia is strongly influenced by the paradigm of the political administration system of government. Indonesia has entered a new phase in the political system of government since the 1998 reform era, which began with the end of the New Order regime. The reform era has led to a fundamental change in the paradigm of forest management in Indonesia. A paradigm shift in the political administration system of the Indonesian state government from a centralized and top-down approach to a participatory-decentralized government approach. This decentralized approach became more evident with the enactment of the Republic of Indonesia Law number 22 of 1999 concerning regional government and the enactment of the Republic of Indonesia Law number 25 of 1999 concerning the balance of central and regional finance.

Along with the paradigm shift in the political administration system of the Indonesian state government in the era of regional autonomy, since the early 2000s, a reorientation of the forestry development paradigm has been carried out as a process of community empowerment to realize equitable and sustainable forest management and prosper the community.

The paradigm shift in the administration of government politics has strategic implications for the roles and responsibilities of the central and regional governments in the implementation of regional autonomy and development for each development sector, including the forestry sector, from state-based forestry to community-based forestry development, from being socially engineered to participatory. State-based forest management systems rely on centralized legal formalities, seeking to increase resource potential in economic, social and ecological aspects. Community base management relies not only on customary law, but also state law and even religious law or known as customary traditions that live informally from the community's cultural view of the natural environment.

The problem of forestry today has grown more and more complicated. Problems and complexities in realizing forest sustainability and community prosperity in parallel can no longer only be solved technically in forestry. Forestry issues have shifted not only to technical issues but also to economic, social, ecological issues and the implications of forestry sector policies which are increasingly complex and dynamic and must be addressed immediately, including their utilization. Meanwhile, the management and utilization of forest

resources by So far, it is suspected that the community's efforts to increase prosperity have not been running optimally.

The forestry development program is basically integrated with the national development program which is implemented based on a decentralized approach and the regulation of national resources which provides opportunities for local governments to improve the community's economy. The implementation of forestry programs in the regions is integrated with development programs and plans formulated and facilitated by the central government. Forestry programs are formulated by considering the suitability and synergy of programs at the national, provincial, district/city and sub-district levels.

The implementation of forestry programs in the regions will be effective if they involve the community in forest utilization. With community participation in forestry programs, a synergistic relationship will be established between the government and the community. The implication is that it has a positive influence in preserving forests, starting from managing forest resources to using forests under the responsibility of the community in an integrated, sustainable and equitable manner.

The management and utilization of customary forest for the community is regulated in customary regulations. Until now, in several regions in Indonesia, customary regulations regarding forest management and use are often encountered, for example, it is not allowed to cut certain trees on certain days (Hardjasoemantri, 2003).

The best way for community-based forest management is to restore the community's role in forest management and protection efforts, restore community rights and encourage the preservation of community culture and wisdom. The community is the main key in the preservation of customary forest areas and sustainable management. The community's interest in customary forests is very high. The community has sufficient traditions, rituals and knowledge to manage and utilize customary forests.

The problem of forests in Southeast Sulawesi is a crucial problem for today's society, there are very few efforts to conserve and utilize existing forest natural resources. Utilization of local wisdom can be an alternative that can be used as a way to conserve forests and utilize forest resources in South Buton Regency.

Forest management carried out by the government unilaterally has in fact resulted in several unfavorable implications from the aspect of managing and conserving forest resources. Thus, the government needs to involve the community in the management and utilization of forest resources. In the management and utilization of customary forests, all elements of governance, such as the private government and the community, must collaborate to create a prosperous and just society by maintaining forest sustainability.

This study examines more specifically community participation in the management and utilization of forest resources in customary forest areas in South Buton district, Southeast Sulawesi, Indonesia.

Literature Review

Community Participation Context

The concept of participation is not a new concept in the field of public administration. The concept of participation began to be widely known in the paradigm of public administration as a science of administration. Community participation is a complex field of study, which gives rise to different views and definitions. The different perspectives of experts on participation are the basis for differences in the definition of participation. Literally, participation means "participation", "participation or participation in an activity.

The classical concept to represent the phenomenon of level or level of participation was originally proposed by Sherry R. Arnstein (Arnstein, 1969) through his work *A Ladder of Citizen Participation* which was published in 1969 through the journal *AIP*. Arnstein's work is a reference for thought and justification for the importance of citizen participation in efforts to implement democratic principles and human rights. Arnstein (1969) compiled a typology of the level of community participation. The classification of this level of participation can be seen as representing the level of community participation. According to Arnstein, the typology of the level of citizen participation can show the structure of power in society and how people interact and who has power in the decision-making process.

Another important development regarding community participation, for example in the UK, community participation has become a central theme in environmental reform policies, where people are expected to participate not only at the environmental level but also at the city level with actors from both public and business organizations (Taylor, 2006).

Public participation is a considerable challenge for countries that have a tradition of centralized management (Erdoğan, et al., 2007). Prior to 1998, the Indonesian government implemented a centralistic, paternalistic, and highly bureaucratic system of government (bureaucratic polity). The implementation of development is loaded with a centralized pattern. This centralized system initially brought success to the development process in Indonesia.

The long application of the centralized approach eventually resulted in a situation where the community's dependence on the government was getting stronger. This then becomes one of the many obstacles to community participation. People are accustomed to a paternalistic-centralistic mentality. People are not used to

taking the initiative; not accustomed to participating in the public interest; not used to managing builds without instructions. This then causes problems in the implementation of the participatory-decentralized paradigm.

Community participation in the context of contemporary public administration theory is one of the dimensions of governance. Public participation is a new approach that emphasizes a two-way interaction between government and society. The concept of governance reflects the phenomenon when the government (government) is no longer the sole actor who organizes government activities. The concept of governance brings together various institutionalized key stakeholder actors. The state as a party to the governance component is all government institutions, both political institutions and public sector institutions. The private sector includes private corporations engaged in various fields and the informal sector. While the community includes professional organizations, community organizations, non-governmental organizations and others.

The importance of community participation according to (Shukor, et al., 2011) can be seen in a wider scope. First, community participation can effectively and efficiently target resources. Second, it can enable two-way communication to provide new ideas. Third, community participation offers new thoughts and innovative ideas from the community. Fourth, community involvement in planning and decision making. Fifth, participation is a process of community empowerment and is a way of planning and sustainable development.

Community participation is a community-based process, when communities organize themselves with their goals at the grassroots level and work together through non-governmental community organizations to influence the decision-making process (Holdar & Zakharchenko, 2002). Community participation is flexibly defined as the process of involving individuals or groups of individuals in society to influence policies that directly affect their own lives (Sumarto, 2009). Many definitions put forward by experts about participation. The main purpose of participation is to involve people in collective and continuous efforts in setting goals, pooling resources together and taking actions aimed at improving living conditions together.

Community Based Forest Resource Management and Utilization

Since the eighth World Forestry Congress in 1978 in Jakarta with the main theme 'Forest for People' by the UN's Food and Agriculture Organization, community-based forest management in the context of customary institutions and their existence for the community has become a central issue and complex discussion that attracted the attention of many parties, both at the national and global levels (Schreckenberg, 1998; Nurarafah, 2001). Since then, in many countries, especially developing countries, community involvement has been a useful approach to forestry development to ensure the conservation of natural resources (Thompson, 1999; Siscawati, 2012).

Indigenous community-based forest management in forest protection and supervision should ideally be a serious concern for central and local governments, because the value system applied in the midst of community life is believed to be still very relevant and effective in realizing community and environmental protection.

As forest owners, the existence of indigenous peoples has an important role in realizing forest conservation. The participation of indigenous peoples in forest protection begins with the recognition of the rights of indigenous peoples over customary forest areas, including in terms of management and utilization. Each group of indigenous peoples has its own traditions and values regarding forest protection and management (Oka, et al., 2008).

Community values become pride, still used from time to time. Several studies have shown that forest management practices with attention to natural resource conservation are more likely to be successful if carried out in the context of customary institutions (Schreckenberg, 1998; Siscawati, 2012).

Each indigenous community has a different identity and uniqueness, this shows the many differences in customs, culture and traditions of the people who grow and develop in Indonesia (Maladi, 2010). This difference and diversity is also found in the management and protection of forest areas. However, the fundamental problem in this regard is that the participation of indigenous peoples often tends to be neglected. The existence of indigenous peoples is often underestimated, especially when investment interest increases in forest areas (Alting, 2011).

The forestry management system in Indonesia, normatively accommodates the social dimension as part of forestry development. The social dimension in forestry development management is included by acknowledging the existence of social communities, as well as giving a participatory role to the community through the legal basis of environmental laws and regulations, and specifically in the forestry sector (Wilujeng, 2015).

Formal Policy on Forest Resource Management

Formal reference to the control of forest resources in Indonesia is based on Article 33 Paragraph 3 of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia: "Earth and water and the natural resources contained therein are controlled by the state for the greatest benefit of the people". It is clearly stated that natural resources are only controlled by the state and implicitly it is also clear that natural resources are public resources. Natural resources are defined as anything that can be taken or utilized from nature because it has useful value to meet human

needs. In dictionary.com, natural resources are defined as the natural wealth of a country, which consists of land, forests, mineral deposits, water, and others.

The Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 41 of 1999 concerning forestry defines forest as an ecosystem unit in the form of a stretch of land containing biological natural resources which is dominated by trees in an inseparable association with one another. The law has also provided an understanding of customary forests, namely forests located within the territory of customary law communities.

Referring to Government Regulation Number 6 of 2007 concerning forest governance and forest management plans and forest utilization, forest utilization is defined as activities to utilize forest areas, utilize environmental services, utilize timber and non-timber forest products in an optimal and fair manner for the welfare of the community while maintaining forest sustainability. Management of forest resources according to Article 21 of the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 41 of 1999 concerning Forestry includes the following activities: a). Forest management and preparation of forest management plans, b). Forest utilization and forest area use, c). Forest rehabilitation and reclamation, d). Forest protection and nature conservation. The purpose of forest management in a broad sense is to achieve the maximum benefit of the forest, either directly or indirectly, to build Indonesian people to improve their welfare.

Some general provisions contained in Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 6 of 2007 concerning Forest Management and Forest Management and Forest Utilization Plans, article 1 paragraph (5) states that forest area utilization is an activity to utilize growing space so that environmental benefits, social benefits, and benefits are obtained. and economic benefits optimally without reducing its main function. Article 1 paragraph (6) states that the use of environmental services is an activity to utilize the potential of environmental services without damaging the environment and reducing its main function. Article 1 paragraph (7) states that the utilization of timber forest products is activities to utilize and cultivate forest products in the form of wood without reducing its main function. Article 1 paragraph (8) states that the utilization of non-timber forest products is an activity to utilize and cultivate forest products in the form of non-timber without damaging the environment and not reducing the main function. Article 1 paragraph (9) states that Timber or non-timber forest product collection is an activity to extract forest products in the form of wood with a certain time limit, area and/or volume. This activity can be carried out in natural or artificial production forests.

The legal basis for forest utilization includes: (1) Article 33 paragraph 3 of the 1945 Constitution which stipulates that the earth, water and natural resources contained therein (including forest resources) shall be utilized as much as possible for the prosperity of the people. (2) CHAPTER V Third Part of Law Number 41 of 1999 concerning Forestry contains provisions relating to forest utilization. (3) Government Regulation Number 6 of 2007 concerning Forest Management and Forest Management Plans and Forest Utilization in conjunction with Government Regulation Number 3 of 2008 (PP No. 3 of 2008) concerning Amendments to Government Regulation Number 6 of 2007.

The purpose of forest utilization based on Law Number 41 of 1999 concerning Forestry and Government Regulation Number 6 of 2007 concerning Forest Management and Forest Management Plans and Forest Utilization is to obtain the benefits of products and services sourced from forest resources in an optimal, fair, and equitable manner. sustainable as much as possible for the welfare of the people.

Method

This research was carried out in the administrative area of South Buton Regency covering Batauga District, Sampolawa District and Lapandewa District which is the scope of the work area of the Lakompa Production Forest Management Unit (KPHP).

The research approach used is a qualitative approach. Data collection method using semi-structured interviews was used to obtain information, data and views from a number of sources. Limited group discussion (FGD) method, which is one of the qualitative approaches chosen to obtain more in-depth data, and validated data sourced from interviews. At the same time, it is more likely to validate data between one informant and another, so that the level of trust in the data becomes better.

This study uses interactive data analysis techniques that include four components of the analysis process that takes place interactively, namely, data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions.

Result and Discussion

South Buton Regency is located in the Buton Archipelago, the southeastern peninsula of Sulawesi Island. South Buton Regency with the central government located in Bataugame is a new Autonomous Region resulting from the expansion of Buton Regency, Southeast Sulawesi Province through the stipulation of Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 16 of 2014. The expansion is to encourage the development and progress of Southeast Sulawesi Province in general and South Buton Regency in particular. The establishment of South Buton Regency is intended to improve government administration, development, and public services as well as

the ability to utilize regional potential in order to accelerate the realization of the welfare of the people of South Buton Regency.

South Buton Regency is mostly located on the island of Buton which is the largest island outside the main island of the Sulawesi Archipelago. South Buton Regency has lowlands and mountains. In this area, the forestry and agricultural sectors play a very significant role. The forest production of South Buton is stem type rattan. The people of South Buton generally work as farmers, fishermen, sailors, traders.

The life of the people of South Buton Regency, especially Batauga District, Sampolawa District and Lapandewa District is very dependent on existing natural resources. Most of the people of South Buton Regency depend on the forest resources around them to meet their economic needs.

Community participation in the management and utilization of customary forests as water resources is relatively high. The people of South Buton Regency know and believe in the importance of managing and utilizing existing customary forests and water resources. The people of South Buton are aware of the importance of the forest as a source of income, resource provider, conservation area, water provider and other functions. This application is also strengthened by binding customary rules. Such as giving sanctions to the community or residents who are proven to have violated or cut down and stole timber in customary forests.

The people of South Buton Regency not only see the forest as a place to earn household economic income but also as a source of food, medicine, and clothing. In an effort to maintain and manage customary forests, the people of South Buton Regency interact and adapt to the surrounding environment, so that the community is actively and voluntarily responsible for maintaining and managing customary forests.

The people of South Buton Regency have long depended on forest products for their lives. In managing and utilizing forest products, the people of South Buton Regency have had signs, namely rules that must be obeyed, both in the use of wood, hunting arrangements, and others. Management based on this wisdom has become a tradition passed down from generation to generation and practiced for a long time.

It is undeniable that the management and utilization of customary forests that are practiced by the people of South Buton Regency have many positive implications for the preservation of customary forests. Community dependence on forest resources causes forest management and utilization activities to focus more on the function of preserving customary forests. It is also relevant considering that the community around the customary forest is a vulnerable and vulnerable element in the event of forest damage which can develop into a threat to the existence of the community around the customary forest.

Forests and the lives of the people of South Buton cannot be separated. The people of South Buton, especially Sampolawa, are still very bound and obedient to customary rules, which are full of beliefs, knowledge and cosmological views regarding the relationship between humans and nature. This cultural view is often found in many activities that intersect between humans and nature in the management of natural resources. The cultural ideas of the South Buton community have several dimensions, such as the dimension of place, the dimension of time, and the dimension of action, each of which has differences and preferential treatment from the community.

Based on these several dimensions, cultural wisdom or ideas in the South Buton community are easily recognized by their characteristics by referring to the dimensions above, such as the existence of traditional names or concepts given by the community to certain activities, the existence of a location or a place in an area that is the right of sacred traditional communities. , the existence of special treatment or action against certain objects, and also usually includes a certain time which is often devoted to being privileged or purified. The use of forest based on community wisdom is still found in most of the people of South Buton. This can be seen from the way the people of South Buton clear land, plant, and harvest.

The management and utilization of forest resources in customary forest areas by the community in a participatory manner still adheres to the applicable customary rules. These regulations are intended so that forest resources such as wood, rattan, resin and others remain available in a sustainable manner for people in need. For example, for the designation of a private house, the type of wood that may be used has been determined so that the felled wood can indeed be used. This provision can minimize illegal logging in customary forest areas.

This cultural view refers to the concept of ecology, which means that between humans and their environment there is a two-way relationship, where humans affect their environment and vice versa. Humans have a great responsibility and influence on changes in the surrounding environment, technological developments and advances from time to time can affect changes in customary forest use patterns, community growth, urbanization, agriculture, economy and socio-culture.

It is seen from the social aspect of the community that wisdom is a tool of social control to respect and appreciate each other, both fellow human beings and the environment. According to Law Number 32 of 2009 concerning Environmental Protection and Management, Wisdom is the noble values that apply in the life of the community, including protecting and managing the environment in a sustainable manner.

The management and utilization of customary forests by the people of South Buton does not fully rely on legal formalities. Customary law and religious law are the original implementation of the social values of the people of South Buton. The values of wisdom in forest management are traditions or known as "customs" that

live from the knowledge of the wisdom of the South Buton people towards nature. Informal approaches are more important in the management and use of customary forests by the people of South Buton.

The people of South Buton, especially Sampolawa, have never exploited forest resources on a large scale. The community only takes forest resources such as wood in the forest for the needs of religious ritual activities or the need to build private houses. The number is very limited, therefore its use is done selectively. Communities use forest resources wisely. Forest products such as timber cut in forest areas cannot be used for commercial purposes.

The tradition-based social system is able to support the sustainable management and utilization of customary forests and forest resources by the community. Formal rules-based forest governance alone in many cases law enforcement is still weak, including unclear existing rules, technical capabilities and less accurate mapping, unclear land tenure, lack of transparency and public participation. However, these weaknesses can be minimized through community-based forest management.

The government, through the Ministry of Environment and Forestry, has opened up opportunities for communities, especially those living in or around forest areas, to manage and utilize their own forest areas. The local government's commitment to community involvement, also related to the policy on structuring customary forest areas, will be the key to achieving the goals of community-based forest management.

Conclusion

The management and utilization of forest resources in the customary forest area by the South Buton people is carried out in a participatory collective manner. The activities of managing and utilizing forest resources are often associated with cultural views about the nature of the relationship between human beings and with nature. culture that is inherited and maintained from generation to generation. Communities use customary forests to obtain ecological, social and economic benefits.

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